

Poverty And Security Situation In Nigeria: An Evaluatory Study

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Abstract

Nigeria is a country endowed with technocrats, intellectuals, and copious amounts of mineral resources. But the vast majority of its people live in extreme poverty due to leadership and insecurity. Poverty has a negative impact on society and even on an individual level; a poor man is a problem for society and even for himself; he is never productive, always angry, and turns to militia activities for support. Poverty is a major contributing factor to insecurity in Nigeria, which this study looks at the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. Using a descriptive method and non-probabilistic sampling techniques. Data were gathered via a survey of six hundred (600) respondents. The study's foundation is derived from the frustration-aggression theory. With the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21, the data were analyzed using correlation and linear regression analysis. Among other findings, the study demonstrated that poverty has a positive and significant relationship ($r = 0.783$) with insecurity in Nigeria. As expected, it also showed that poverty has a positive and statistically significant impact ($r^2 = 0.716$) on insecurity in Nigeria. Consequently, the study suggests that the Nigerian government, at all levels, should prioritize the welfare of the people by addressing their basic needs.

Keywords: Nigeria, Security, Insecurity, Poverty, Frustration, Aggression

Introduction

Nigeria is the biggest producer of oil in Africa and the sixth oil producer in the world but despite its vast resources, it ranks among the poorest countries in the world. A recent World Bank (2010) report released at a United Nations summit rated her as second poorest country in the world with most Nigerians living below poverty line. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS 2012) about 60.9% of Nigerians in 2010 were living in 'absolute poverty'. In 2011, the figure rose slightly to 61.9% and in BBC news (2012), the number of Nigerians living in poverty was put at 61%. The highest poverty rates are recorded in the North-West and North-East geopolitical zones with a poverty rate of 77.7% and 76.6% respectively (NBS 2012). The reason is not far-fetched considering that these zones are riddled with conflicts. Absence of basic services, unemployment, bad governance and corruption, provide an avenue for disgruntled members of the society to be radicalized.

Insecurity in the North led to the declaration of a state of emergency in three states in the zone namely; Yobe, Adamawa and Bornu states. Despite this, the killing continues and the worst aspect of it is that in recent times, educational institutions have become targets with many male students killed and hundreds of young girls abducted. Besides, there is a spill-over effect with insecurity spilling over to other parts of the North like Zamfara state which had for long been a peaceful state compared to other states in the North. On Saturday 5th April, 2014, about 112 people were reported killed by insurgents who stormed Yar'galadima village in Dansadau District of Maru LGA of the state (DailyTrust Newspaper April 7, 2014).

Poverty is a cause and effect of conflicts between Niger Delta's minority ethnic groups and Multinational Oil Companies (MNOCs) with the former who felt they were being shortchanged and demanded for a share of the 'petrol dollar' as compensation for environmental degradation among others. The violence that erupted as a result of this has not only led to the destruction of means of livelihood but in most cases the loss of bread winners. In addition, it has impeded business investments in the areas of economic growth and productivity, encouraged inflation and unemployment affected negatively the living standards of the people. As a result of disenchantment with the activities of MNOCs, various militant groups in the Niger Delta emerged and resorted to abducting foreign oil workers for ransom (Okorie, Onyema and Bassey, 2019).

In the North Central Zone, insecurity is also rife. In places like Plateau state, conflict between the Hausa-Fulani and the Berom people has left many dead while in Benue state the recent conflict between the Fulani herdsmen and the local people led to many deaths and villages being sacked. Nasarawa state is another conflict-ridden state in the Zone. Communal conflicts have become pervasive to the extent that virtually every local government area has an unresolved conflict at various stages of escalation or de-escalation (Ayih, 2003; Gyuse and Ajene, 2006). There is conflict between the Eggon-Koro/Migiliin Obi Local Government, the Alagos and Hausa are locked in internecine conflict with the Tiv Community in Awe Local Government over land matters while there is conflict in Nasarawa Local Government between the indigenous Afo and the Hausa/Fulani over chieftaincy dispute. Insecurity in the regions no doubt affects the nation's national income as it discourages investors (Okorie, Onyema and Bassey, 2019).

In South-East region, conflict between Herders and Farmers which had claimed lives and property in Nimbo community in Uzo-Uwani Local government area of Enugu state in

2016 is another dimension of insecurity. Also, the incessant kidnapping/ killings along UgwuOgo Nike Opi-Agu/Agu Ekwegbe Nsukka road is another dimension of insecurity in the country. Many farmers could not attend to the farming activities as a result of insecurity, which metamorphosed into the increase in poverty rate to the entire zone. Fear of the unknown attacks dwindle and retard the supply of food from the rural areas to the urban settlement, which increases poverty and hunger. Imo state has been another dungeon of insecurity and kidnapping in the South-East. On this note, this paper tries to investigate the impact of poverty on security in Nigeria

Statement of the Problem

Despite having an abundance of intellectuals, technocrats, and natural wealth, the majority of Nigerians live in extreme poverty. Financial crimes, transnational organized crimes, armed robberies and other related thefts, kidnappings, farmers-herdsmen clashes, political assassinations, vandalism of government infrastructure, insurgency by Niger Delta Militant, and terrorism by Boko Haram Sect are just a few of the crimes that Nigeria has witnessed recently (Adegoke, 2015; Osawe, 2015). One of the reasons behind the formation of a militia group that uses improvised explosive devices (IEDs) and heavy weapons is poverty. It has grown to be a significant issue that is acknowledged both domestically and globally, that needs immediate action, particularly in Sub-Saharan African nations like Nigeria. Because of the nation's high level of corruption and institutional fragility, majority of Nigerians live in substandard conditions that have become phobic and defied all solutions presented (Ikyase and Namo, 2018).

In Nigeria, poverty's effects are widespread and can result in violent act. For instance, a destitute individual poses a challenge to both society and himself and he is constantly irate, unproductive, while being desperate to survive by joining a militia. This could be due to economic marginalization, unemployment, inequality, and a lack of education. In light of this, this study explores the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria and identifies the policy measures that governments should take to combat poverty and deal with the seemingly unabated and multifaceted insecurity in order to prevent unintended consequences that could jeopardize Nigeria's very existence as a federation.

Objectives of the Study:

The following study objectives and null hypotheses were developed in accordance with the literature review.

- i. To examine the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria
- ii.

To evaluate the effect of poverty on insecurity in Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of poverty on insecurity in Nigeria?

Hypotheses of the Study:

H1: There is no significant relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria H2:

Poverty does not have a significant effect on insecurity in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Poverty

The concept of poverty has evolved over time and differs in extent and magnitude amongst countries. It has therefore become extremely difficult to come up with definitions that are universally accepted (Akwara, Akwara, Enwuchola, Adekunle & Udaw, 2013). Nonetheless, there are widely recognized measures of what defines poverty. The widely recognized definition of absolute, relative, and material poverty divides these variables into three major groups. The incapacity of an individual or community to supply necessities for bodily sustenance and preservation of human dignity, such as clothing, food, housing, and clean water, as well as basic education, transportation, and gainful employment, is known as absolute poverty. It decreases one's involvement in society to the point where it hinders the realization of personal potentials.

Poverty can be defined as a state of not having access to healthcare, income, or empowerment. Nwagwu (2014) asserts that "to be poor is to be powerless." It also implies being scorned and denigrated. It entails receiving unfair treatment. Above all, it denotes a dearth of elements that contribute to sound physical and mental health. Karl Marx observed that economics is the key to the class system. Therefore, poverty is an extreme condition in which a person is unable to take advantage of the resources available to him in order to better himself in any way—be it socially, politically, economically, or otherwise (Okorie, Onyema and Bassey, 2019).

Insecurity

It would be better to start with introducing the idea of security in order to fully comprehend the concept of insecurity. The definition of this is "the existence of conditions within which people in a society can go about their normal daily activities without any threats to their lives or properties," according to Ogunleye, Adewale, Alese, and Ogunde (2011), referenced in Ighomereho and Akpo-Robaro (2015:80). To put it simply, security is the safeguarding of individuals' lives and belongings within the political community. It is a state's primary justification for existing (Ikyase & Namo, 2018). Security, on the other hand, can also be defined as follows: safety or protection from psychological harm stemming from the assurance that one is wanted, accepted, loved, and protected in one's community or neighborhood and by people around; predictability of daily life (knowing what to expect); protection from crime (feeling safe); and freedom from instability and continuity of livelihood (stable and steady income).

According to Nwanegbo, Umara, and Ikyase (2017) security is the ability to shield the populace from famine, illness, unemployment, poverty, and natural calamities. A high standard of living is enjoyed by the populace in nations where the proper development paradigm is in place and being followed. This is evidenced by the government's willingness to provide jobs, portable water, electricity, affordable housing, decent food, and roads, among other basic

necessities. A lack of dread, threat, worry, tension, and apprehension over the loss of life, liberty, goals, and values is likely to occur in a secure environment. Thus, security entails tackling Nigerians' extreme material poverty.

Therefore, insecurity can be defined as an act that could endanger one's life or cause pain or make life unpleasant, it is the opposite of security. However, the concept of insecurity has typically been assigned multiple interpretations in relation with the many ways in which it impacts individuals or groups due to the myriad ways in which it influences human life and existence. Loss of safety, risk, hazard, uncertainty, loss of confidence, questionable, insufficiently guarded or protected, unstable, disturbed, lack of protection, and dangerous are some common descriptors of insecurity (Kukati, 2012).

Ighomereho and Akpor-Robaro (2015), characterizes insecurity as "a condition of anxiety or fear resulting from a real or perceived absence of safety." To put it succinctly, insecurity is the state of being vulnerable to injury and loss of life, property, or source of income. Nigeria is currently dealing with a number of issues, including escalating incidents of insecurity, a recurring pattern of attacks on individuals, and agitations stemming from ethnic divisions. The nation is facing challenges related to survival, stability, and security as a result of a number of ongoing insecurity cases in Nigeria, such as the roving herdsmen militancy, the new face of militancy in the Niger Delta, the Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East, the vocal separatist agitations in the South-East, and the recent wave of kidnappings, armed robberies, abductions, and other violent crimes (Nwanegbo et al., 2017).

Poverty and Insecurity in Nigeria

According to Adegoke (2015), there is a correlation between unemployment and the rise in crimes, terrorism, and sectarian violence. Nwagwu (2014) suggests that unemployment leads to poverty. Poverty leads to a high prevalence of state insecurity in Nigeria, which borders on armed robberies, kidnappings, abductions, and other criminal activities, as well as ethno-religious disputes and the difference between indigenous people and settlers. In Nigeria, unemployment and poverty have been major contributing factors to the emergence of multiple ethno-religious crises. This is due to the nation's massive reservoir of impoverished individuals who, frustrated, are easily available to belligerents and eager to act as mercenary combatants (Nwagwu, 2014).

Ighodalo (2012) submitted that "one of the main causes of the nation's political, social, and economic strife is poverty." Poverty is incompatible with the values and fundamental principles of democracy. When there is enough around, poverty breeds discontent and pushes people into violence. The people's capacity to make autonomous decisions and actively engage in the decision-making process is restricted, and their self-worth is diminished as well as their capacity to hold elected officials accountable. The relentless growth of youth militias in Nigeria is a result of poverty (Jike, 2017). This bolsters the claim made by Nwagwu (2024) that young people without salary-earning jobs comprised the Niger Delta youths, the Oduduwa People's Congress (OPC), the movement for the Actualization of Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), and the resurgence of Boko-Haram, a faceless religious sect devoid of ideology

Similarly, Nwagbosa (2013) maintains that one of the main reasons for insecurity in Nigeria is the inability of the country's successive administrations to address issues of poverty,

unemployment, and unequal wealth distribution among ethnic groups. Despite the numerous policies and initiatives put in place by the various governments of Nigeria, including the Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP), the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), National Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), SURE-P, N-Power, Trader money, among others may seem, their failure to impact the intended audience—young people—reflects the gap that exists in Nigeria between the formulation of policy and its actual execution. According to Maduagwu, (2006), referenced in Toby and Akani (2014), among the reasons why previous attempts to reduce poverty in Nigeria were unsuccessful were the following:

- (i) The politics of personal rule is a unique kind of political system where the main factors influencing political life are not impersonal institutions, ideologies, public politics, or class interests, but rather the rivalries and conflicts of strong, determined men.
- (ii) The Abuja method's top-down, big-men strategy, which emphasizes the master-servant dynamic in poverty alleviation initiatives. Studies have linked Nigeria's high rate of poverty to a deeper, more significant issue than just the country's rising crime rate (Osawe, 2015; Etim, Duke & Ogbinyi, 2017). Thus, there is a clear connection between Nigeria's high rate of property and life insecurity and poverty.

Theoretical Framework

The adoption of frustration-aggression Theory provides the theoretical foundation for examining how poverty affects insecurity in the state of Nigeria. This traditional view explains why people commit violent crimes (riots, rebellions, coups, etc.), particularly young people. A variety of sources of frustration, including a lack of money or the inability to get respect as a result of economic disadvantages, have been linked to juvenile criminality, particularly among lower-class kids (Greenberg, 1977). The frustration-aggression theory, which contends that frustration is only the act of blocking someone from making an advancement, development, or achievement in life, further supports this premise by suggesting that this obstruction almost certainly results in discontent when a person or group chooses to respond violently (aggression) in order to express disapproval of obstacles to their success. These can lead to sentiments of rage, which can then result in violent conduct and feelings of aggression (Zumve, Ingyoroko, & Akuva, 2013).

Anger, or the emotional willingness to act aggressively, is produced when frustration gives rise to animosity. Adegoke (2015) quoted Ivo and Feierabend, 1972, who used the frustration-aggression theory to examine political instability in 84 different countries. It was shown that individuals in quickly developing modern countries become more conscious of material improvement as they get more urbanized and have higher levels of literacy, as is the case in Nigeria today. The state's incapacity to coordinate its efforts and fulfill its fundamental duty of safeguarding its population has been greatly attributed, among other reasons, to its incapacity to manage insecure situations. Nigeria may be considered a Fragile State given the increasing wave of instability that is sweeping the entire nation. According to Sara (2008), a country that has significant developmental issues such limited institutional capacity, bad governance, political instability, unemployment, low economic development, and poverty is referred to as being in a fragile state.

Leading proponent of the frustration-aggression theory in Nigeria, Salawu (2010), contends that "the unfortunate breakdown of such indigenous vehicles of social control of human behaviors that characterized the Traditional African Societies, such as the family units, pre-school age indigenous education and native laws, religion and traditional political system that molds human behavior, is one of the major causes of what we now see as ethnoreligious conflicts in Nigeria." conventional governmental structure that fosters moral character, values human life, and prioritizes the welfare of all constituents. The breakdown of these established institutions has led to a rise in violent crimes, including Boko Haram insurgency in the NorthEast, ethnic and communal conflicts, loud separatist protests in the South-East, and a new face of militancy among herdsmen in the Niger Delta. It has also seriously jeopardized the basic foundation and continued existence of state security agents in Nigeria. He connected the failed state to widespread unemployment, illiteracy, and poverty, which drove people—especially young people—to turn to crime as a means of subsistence. In Nigeria, violent conflicts and criminal activity are direct results of anger, which is directly linked to poverty.

METHODOLOGY

The aimed of the study was to examine the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. The descriptive methods and causal research design were adopted and data was collected via a survey of 600 respondents comprises of Christian leaders, Muslim leaders, leaders of Civil Society groups, Traditional leaders and Youth leaders randomly selected in each geopolitical zones as shown below.

Table 1: Population of the Study

Variable s	NorthWe st	NorthCent ra l	NorthEa st	SouthWe st	SouthSout h	SouthEa st	Tota l
Christian Leaders	Sokoto (20)	Plateau (20)	Taraba (20)	Lagos (20)	Bayelsa (20)	Ebony i(20)	120
Muslim Leaders	Kaduna (20)	Kwara (20)	Adama wa (20)	Osun (20)	Akwa- Ibom (20)	Anambra (20)	120
Civil Society Groups Leaders	Zamfara (20)	Niger (20)	Bauchi (20)	Oyo (20)	Rivers (20)	Enugu (20)	120
Tradition al Leaders	Kebbi (20)	Kogi (20)	Borno (20)	Ogun(20)	Delta (20)	Abia(20)	120
Youth Leaders	Kano (20)	FCT (20)	Yobe (20)	Ekiti (20)	Edo (20)	Imo (20)	120
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	600

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2024

Sampling Technique

The positive non-probabilistic method was adopted to target respondents with knowledge about the specific issues captured in the study. The sample was drawn from the six geopolitical zones to elicit views on the relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using correlation and linear regression analysis with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.

Reliability and Validity of the Instruments

A structured questionnaire was designed to elicit needed information from the respondents. The reliability was established through a trial test conducted on 40 respondents in the SouthSouth zone who also took part in the study. Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument as shown in the table below.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics of variables

Scale	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Poverty	9	0.753
Insecurity	11	0.714

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024

The results yielded a coefficient of 0.753 and 0.714, which satisfied the general recommended level of 0.70 for the research indicators (Cronbach, 1951). Experts also judged the face and content validity of the questionnaire as adequate. Hence, researchers' satisfied both the reliability and validity of the scale.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 3: Distribution of Questionnaire and Response Rate

S/N	Geopolitical zones	Questionnaire Distributed	Questionnaire Retrieved	Percentage (%)
1	North-West	100	51	8.5
2	North-Central	100	66	11.0
3	North-East	100	42	7.0
4	South-West	100	62	10.3
5	South-South	100	75	12.5
6	South-East	100	69	11.5
	Total	600	365	60.8

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, 2024

Out of the 600 questionnaires administered across the six (6) geopolitical zones, 365 were retrieved and analyzed given us a response rate of 60.8%. While a total of 235

questionnaires representing 39.2% were not returned. This indicated that majority of the questionnaire distributed across the states of the Federation were returned and were utilized for the study as presented in this study.

Table 4: Correlation Metrix

Variables		Poverty	Insecurity
Poverty	Pearson Correlation	1	.883**
	Sig. (2-tailed) N	365	.000 365
Insecurity	Pearson Correlation	.883**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed) N	.000 365	365

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2-tailed)

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 shows the correlation between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. There exists a significant positive high correlation between poverty and insecurity ($r = .883$, $n = 365$, & $P < 0.005$). This implies that poverty has a strong and positive relationship with insecurity in Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5: Moderated Linear Regression Analysis showing the Effect of the Independent Variable on the Dependent Variable.

Independ ent Variable	R ²	Adj . R ²	Co- effic ient	F- stat	R. Sig.	T- stat	Tsi g.	D.W
Poverty	.78 5	.74 3	.319	22.5 13	.00 0 ^a	.21 2	.00 0	1.92 7

Source: Researcher’s Fieldwork, 2024

In table 5, drawing on the model summary displayed by the linear regression analysis, we observed that R² value which is the coefficient determination was 0.785. This implies that poverty accounts for a 78.5% increase in insecurity in Nigeria. While the remaining 21.5% causes of change in insecurity are explained by other factors not included in the model, but taken care of by error turns. The Adjusted R² value which was 0.743 in the linear regression model further indicated that coefficient of determination, when adjusted for the degree of freedom, yielded approximately 74.3%. The Durbin Watson statistic, which is 1.927, implies the absence of serial autocorrelation in the regression analysis and therefore, the model can be relied upon in making policies related to the subject matter. The F-statistic value of 22.513 at $\text{prob}(\text{sig.}) = .000^a$ conducted at 5% level of significant depicted in the regression results revealed that overall, there exists a statistically significant linear relationship between poverty and

insecurity in Nigeria. Similarly, the T-statistic of $-.212$ at P-value (sig.) of $.000$ obtained in the model which is less than 5% or 0.05 level of significant also indicated that there is a significant relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. The coefficient of 0.319 further indicated that a one percent increase in poverty results in a 31.9% increase in insecurity in Nigeria.

FINDINGS

Research indicates that violence, animosity, and insecurity are fostered by poverty and inequality in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The results amongst others revealed that there is a strong and positive relationship between poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Osawe (2015) and Etimetal's (2017) studies which revealed a direct relationship between poverty and insecurity. As predicted, the results also showed that poverty exerts a positive and statistically significant impact on insecurity in Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Ighodalo's (2012), Nwagwu's (2014), Adekoge's (2015) and Jike's (2017) views that poverty is responsible for the spate of insecurity of lives and properties in Nigeria. Good governance is the main function of an effective, visionary, transparent, trustworthy, and credible leadership whose motivation is to improve the general well-being of the populace through carefully thought out, skillfully carried out economic policies and human development initiatives. Consequently, accelerating economic growth and reducing insecurity are necessary to end poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. Taking into account should be devoted to incorporating poverty alleviation into the country's broader development/policy management framework and making it an explicit constitutional problem.

Conclusions

The study's apparent conclusions have demonstrated that poverty in Nigeria significantly influenced insecurity. Furthermore, it was established that poverty and insecurity are significantly related in Nigeria. From the study's results, we deduced that poverty in an affluent environment breeds discontent and violent behavior, limits people's capacity to make their own decisions and actively engage in the political process, lowers people's self-esteem, and makes it harder for them to hold those in positions of power accountable. Those who lack the funds and other necessities for a comfortable living—such as access to quality healthcare, wholesome food, a place to live, clothes, and other social amenities—are considered impoverished.

The gap between policy formation and implementation in Nigeria is evident in the numerous policies and programs, no matter how lofty and admirable they may seem, that have not been able to impact the real target, the youth despite being launched by successive Nigerian governments. Examples of these programs and policies include the Better Life Programme (BLP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Family Support Programme (FSP), Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs), National Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), SURE-P, N-Power, Trader money, etc.

Recommendations

The following policy recommendations were offered in light of the study's theoretical and empirical findings:

1. To guarantee Nigeria's political stability, economic stability, supply of sufficient social services, and other infrastructure development, the government at all levels should step up its efforts. It should be thought about include poverty alleviation in the country's overall development/policy management framework and making it an explicit constitutional concern.
2. All levels of government should enact laws to shield the populace from hunger, disease, unemployment, natural disasters, poverty, and other threats. The grassroots population should also be sufficiently involved in the selection and execution of projects and initiatives that have an impact on their daily lives.
3. The federal and state governments need to come up with practical plans to use the nation's resources to generate income and jobs in order to lower poverty. It is necessary to amend the 1999 Constitution, which restricts the states and centre

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